

Multilateral Development Banks Driving Green Transition in Emerging Markets

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Key Points

- The study examines how green bonds support low-carbon growth and Sustainable Development Goals in emerging economies, using Morocco as a case study to explore strategies for advancing green finance.
- It applies a risk-resilience framework and strategic thematic analysis to investigate institutional dynamics shaping green bond markets, focusing on the role of multilateral development banks (MDBs) in supporting national issuers and addressing market challenges.
- The Moroccan case highlights opportunities and constraints for domestic actors engaging with international green finance frameworks.
- The findings provide practical insights for policymakers and financial institutions in developing regions to enhance the structure and impact of sustainable finance.

Introduction

By adopting the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, the world community pledged to drastically alter the production and consumption of goods and services, increase the efficiency of resource use, and ensure that economic expansion does not result in environmental gradation.

The green economy, as a concept, lacks a universally accepted definition on an international scale. This concept is multifaceted and integrates economic growth, social advancement, and ecological sustainability. According to the Rio 20 Conference, it is viewed as a way to promote more sustainable development and lessen inequality and poverty. For the United Nations Environment Programme

(UNEP), a green economy is one that significantly reduces ecological risks and resource scarcity while promoting social justice and well-being.

To create a sustainable financial market, governments can use several strategies:

- a. Changes in national managerial decisions and frameworks,
- b. Harmonising public financial incentives,
- c. Increasing investment in environmentally friendly projects
- d. Enhancing IT infrastructure for AI-driven green technologies,
- e. Supporting climate and sustainable natural energy resource economies,
- f. Increasing the use of new instruments like clean equities, green loans, village funds, and green bonds.

Each of these strategies aligns with UNEP's approach to the promotion of green financing (Lee 2020). Thus, green finance can come from multiple sources, e.g. banks, non-financial commercial companies, government agencies, and non-profit organisations, which qualifies it as a subset of sustainable finance since it considers social, managerial, and environmental implications.

Whichever description is used; it is crucial to keep in mind that the green transition is a component of a new trajectory of long-term, socially inclusive growth that is predicated on maintaining environmental balances and effectively managing natural resources over the long term. This growing urgency to address environmental challenges has spurred the development of innovative financial instruments. Green finance, encompassing a wide range of tools and approaches, has emerged as a critical force in promoting sustainable development.

However, the obstacle to green transition remains in how to effectively finance green projects. In fact, creating a market framework capable of efficiently rallying government and financial bodies to back green initiatives have emerged as a point of interest, often lacking a profound understanding of the market dynamics necessary to sustain robust economic outcomes.

Raising capital for environmentally friendly projects is one of the main responsibilities of Moroccan financial institutions. With a goal of producing 52% of its electricity from renewable sources by 2030, Morocco has set high goals for renewable energy. A substantial investment in solar, wind, and other renewable energy technologies is necessary to meet this aim. Development banks in particular are in a good position to encourage private sector funding for these projects by using financial tools such as guarantees and concessional loans (Dalhuijsen et al., 2023).

Our study is set within this framework and motivated by prevalent literature findings that emphasise the significant link between the issuance of green bonds